

DISTANCE-EDGE-MONITORING NUMBER OF COMPLETE SPLIT GRAPHS

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Abstract: In this paper the distance-edge-monitoring problem, which is recently introduced, is studied for special class of graphs, named complete split graphs $K_{k,n-k}^*$. We are stated and proved formula for the distance-edge-monitoring number for these graphs and its exact value is equal to k .

Keywords: Distance-edge-monitoring number, complete split graphs, graph theory, discrete mathematics.

1. INTRODUCTION

The distance-edge-monitoring problem was first introduced in (Foucaud et al., 2022). Let $G = (V, E)$ be a simple connected undirected graph with vertex set V and edge set E . Then, a set M of vertices of a graph G is called a distance-edge-monitoring set if, for every edge e in G , there exists a vertex x from M and a vertex y from G such that e is part of all shortest paths between x and y . The set M with minimal cardinality is called the distance-edge-monitoring set of the graph and the smallest size of such set in graph G is denoted by $dem(G)$. The vertices in M serve as monitoring points within a network represented by G . When an edge e fails, the shortest path distance between x and y increases, allowing us to detect the failure. Interestingly, not only can we identify that an edge has failed, but we can also pinpoint exactly which edge is affected.

In (Foucaud et al., 2022), it is showed that for a nontrivial connected graph G of order n holds $1 \leq dem(G) \leq n - 1$ and it is equal to 1 if and only if G is a tree, while it is equal to $n - 1$ if and only if it is a complete graph. The authors computed the exact value of distance-edge-monitoring number for grid, hypercubes and complete bipartite graphs. Moreover, it is characterized graphs G with $dem(G) = 2$. Also, the authors provides both lower and upper bounds for $dem(G)$. Finally, the authors proved that determining $dem(G)$ for graph G is an *NP*-complete problem in a general case.

In (Kartelj et al., 2024), it presents an exact procedure, based on an integer linear programming model, to determine the probe set with the smallest number of elements. They proposed the first-ever integer programming model for distance-edge-monitoring problem and they presented empirical results for five classes of graphs, where the maximum number of vertices is 4096 and the maximum number of edges is 1599797. The effectiveness of this approach is demonstrated using random graphs that resemble real-world networks. However, the authors highlight that their method is not tailored to a specific type of graph, making it applicable in a broad range of case.

There are several related paper for distance-edge-monitoring problem in the literature. In the article (Liet al., 2025), the authors presented upper and lower bounds for Cartesian graph products, and in the cases where upper and lower bounds could be obtained, they provided a characterization of graphs that reach these bounds. In article (C. Yang, Klasing, Mao, and Deng, 2024), it also provides the lower and upper bounds for $P(M, e)$, $EM(x)$ and $dem(G)$, as well as the characterization of the graphs on which they are reach.

After initial works, we will mention some additional papers that study distance-edge-monitoring problem from various theoretical and practical perspectives, such as (C. Yang, Klasing, He, and Mao, 2023), (G. Yang and He, 2023) and (Lepič, 2022).

Next, some theoretical properties of distance-edge-monitoring problem, which documented in the literature, will be presented, which is used in the following section.

1.1. Definitions and basic properties

For graph $G = (V, E)$, distance between two vertices u and v , where $u, v \in V$, is the length of the shortest path between this vertices in G and denoted as $d_G(u, v)$.

Definition 1. (Foucaud et al., 2022) For a set M of vertices and an edge e of a graph G , let $P(M, e)$ be the set of pairs (x, y) with x a vertex of M and y a vertex of $V(G)$ such that $d_G(x, y) \neq d_{G-e}(x, y)$. In other words, e belongs to all shortest paths between x and y in G .

Definition 2. (Foucaud et al., 2022) For a vertex x , let $EM(x)$ be the set of edges e such that there exists a vertex $v \in V(G)$ with $(x, v) \in P(x, e)$.

If $e \in EM(x)$, we say that e is monitored by x .

Definition 3. (Foucaud et al., 2022) A set M of vertices of a graph G is distance-edge-monitoring if every edge e of $E(G)$ is monitored by some vertex of M , i.e., the set $P(M, e)$ is nonempty. Equivalently, $\bigcup_{x \in M} EM(x) = E(G)$.

An integer linear programming (ILP) model of the distance-edge-monitoring problem is given in the paper (Kartelj et al., 2024). The proposed integer programming model is:

$$\min \sum_{v \in V} x_v \tag{1}$$

s.t.

$$\sum_{v \in V} C_{v,e} \cdot x_v \geq 1, \text{ for } e \in E \tag{2}$$

$$x_v \in \{0,1\}, \text{ for } v \in V \tag{3}$$

The variable x_v , for $v \in V$, equals 1 if the vertex v is included in the distance-edge-monitoring set, otherwise, it equals 0. Hence, if $x_v = 1$ for some $v \in V$, then $v \in M$. Evidently, the objective function (1) relates to the formulation of a distance-edge-monitoring set problem.

The constant $C_{v,e}$ for $(v, e) \in V \times E$ equals 1 if for a pair (v, e) there exists a vertex $u \in V$ so that edge e belongs to all the shortest paths between vertices v and u . Practically, if $e \in EM(v)$ then $C_{v,e} = 1$, i.e. $C_{v,e} = 0$ when $e \notin EM(v)$. Constraints (2) impose the distance-edge-monitoring condition and that meaning that for every $e \in E$, there must be at least one $v \in M$ that monitors it.

It should be noted that $V(G)$ is always a distance-edge-monitoring set of G , so $dem(G)$ is always well-defined.

Definition 4. A Complete split graph $K_{k,n-k}^*$ has vertices $V(K_{k,n-k}^*) = V_1 \cup V_2$, where $V_1 = \{v_1, \dots, v_k\}$ and $V_2 = \{v_{k+1}, \dots, v_n\}$. Edges $E(K_{k,n-k}^*) = E_1 \cup E_2$, where $E_1 = \{v_i v_j | 1 \leq i < j \leq k\}$ and $E_2 = \{v_i v_j | 1 \leq i \leq k, k+1 \leq j \leq n\}$.

It is easy to calculate that these graphs have n vertices and $\binom{n}{2} - \binom{n-k}{2}$ edges. It should be noted that the diameter of these graphs is two and only shortest paths between two vertices from V_2 has length 2. All other shortest paths are trivial, with length 1.

Figure 1: Graph $K_{4,3}^*$

The distance-edge-monitoring sets are relaxations of vertex covers. A vertex cover C of a graph G is defined as a set of vertices where each edge in G has at least one of its endpoints included in C . The minimum size of

a vertex cover for graph G is denoted as $vc(G)$. In some graphs, every distance-edge-monitoring set qualifies a vertex cover.

Theorem 1. (Foucaud et al., 2022) *In any graph G of order n , any vertex cover of G is a distance-edge-monitoring set, and thus $dem(G) \leq vc(G) \leq n - 1$. Moreover, we have $dem(G) = n - 1$ if and only if G is the complete graph of order n .*

Theorem 2. (Foucaud et al., 2022) *Let G be a connected graph with at least one edge. We have $dem(G) = 1$ if and only if G is a tree.*

Corollary 1. (Foucaud et al., 2022) *We have $dem(K_{a,b}) = vc(K_{a,b}) = \min\{a, b\}$ and $dem(H_d) = vc(H_d) = 2^{d-1}$.*

2. NEW THEORETICAL RESULTS

In the next theorem it will be obtained and proved distance-edge-monitoring number of any complete split graph $K_{k,n-k}^*$.

Theorem 3. For $k \geq 2$ and $n \geq k + 2$, it holds $dem(K_{k,n-k}^*) = k$.

Proof. *Step 1.* $dem(K_{k,n-k}^*) \leq k$

Let $M = V_1$. We will find $P(M, e)$ for all edges from $E(K_{k,n-k}^*)$.

If $e \in E_1$ then it be noted as $e = uv$ with $u \in V_1$ and $v \in V_1$. Then, $P(M, e) = P(V_1, uv)$ is the set of pairs (x, y) with $x \in V_1$ and $y \in V_1 \cup V_2$ such that uv belongs to all shortest paths between x and y in G . Since $x \in V_1$ and $y \in V_1 \cup V_2$ so $d(x, y) = 1 \Rightarrow x = u, y = v$ implying $P(M, e) = P(V_1, uv) = \{(u, v)\}$.

If $e \in E_2$ then it be noted as $e = uw$ with $u \in V_1$ and $w \in V_2$. Then, $P(M, e) = P(V_1, uw)$ is the set of pairs (x, y) with $x \in V_1$ and $y \in V_1 \cup V_2$ such that uw belongs to all shortest paths between x and y in G . The fact $x \in V_1$ and $y \in V_1 \cup V_2$ so $d(x, y) = 1 \Rightarrow x = u, y = w$ implying $P(M, e) = P(V_1, uw) = \{(u, w)\}$.

Since, for each $e \in E(K_{k,n-k}^*) = E_1 \cup E_2$, it holds $P(M, e) = P(V_1, e) \neq \emptyset$, then by Definition 2 set $M = V_1$ is distance-edge-monitoring for graph $K_{k,n-k}^*$, implying $dem(K_{k,n-k}^*) \leq k$.

Step 2. $dem(K_{k,n-k}^*) \geq k$

Let we fix set M^* such that $|M^*| \leq k - 1$. We will find $P(M^*, e)$ for each edge from $E(K_{k,n-k}^*)$. Since $|M^*| \leq k - 1$ then there exists vertex $u \in V_1$ such that $u \notin M^*$. Moreover, there exists another vertex $v \in V_1$, such that $v \notin M^*$ or vertex $w \in V_2$, such that $w \notin M^*$. In first case, for edge $e = uv$, it holds $P(M^*, e) = \emptyset$ since $u, v \notin M^*$ so edge $e = uv$ do not belongs to any shortest path of length l between $x \in M^*$ and $y \in V(K_{k,n-k}^*)$ because:

- $l = 1 \Rightarrow x = u \wedge y = v$ but $x \in M^*$ while $u \notin M^*$;
- $l = 2 \Rightarrow$ edge uv with $u, v \in V_1$ could not includes in any shortest paths of length 2.

In second case, for edge $e = uw$, it holds $u, w \notin M^*$, so edge $e = uw$ could only belongs to shortest path $x - u - w$ with $y = w$ of length 2 between $x \in M^*$ and $y \in V(K_{k,n-k}^*)$. On the other hand, for any $z \in V_1 \wedge z \neq u$ other shortest path $x - z - w$ between x and $y = w$ could not include edge uw , so $P(M^*, e) = \emptyset$.

In both cases is $P(M^*, e) = \emptyset$, so M^* is not a distance-edge-monitoring set for graph $K_{k,n-k}^*$. Since there no exist a distance-edge-monitoring set of cardinality less than k , then it holds $dem(K_{k,n-k}^*) \geq k$. \square

Further, it should be discussed two special situations of degenerated complete split graphs:

- $k = 1$: It is easy to see that $K_{1,n-1}^* \cong S_n$, where S_n is a star with n vertices. Then, by Theorem 2, since S_n is a tree, we have the following result $dem(K_{1,n-1}^*) = dem(S_n) = 1$;
- $n - k = 1$: It is easy to see that $K_{n-1,1}^* \cong K_n$. Then, by Theorem 1, we have the following result $dem(K_{n-1,1}^*) = dem(K_n) = n - 1$.

3. CONCLUSION

In this paper the exact value of distance-edge-monitoring number of the complete split graphs is stated and proved. For $k \geq 2$ and $n \geq k + 2$ distance-edge-monitoring number of each complete split graph $K_{k,n-k}^*$ is equal k . Future work can be directed towards solving ongoing research on complete split graphs or determining the exact value of the distance-edge-monitoring number of some related graphs.

LITERATURE

- Foucaud, F., Kao, S.-S., Klasing, R., Miller, M., & Ryan, J. (2022). Monitoring the edges of a graph using distances. *Discrete Applied Mathematics*, 319, 424–438.
- Kartelj, A., Filipović, V., & Kratica, J. (2024). Integer programming model for distance-edge-monitoring problem. *Yugoslav Journal of Operations Research*. <https://doi.org/10.2298/YJOR230815016K>
- Lepič, V. (2022). Distance edge monitoring set problem with respect to structural parameters. B.S. thesis, Faculty of Information Technology CTU in Prague, Department of Theoretical Computer Science.
- Li, W., Klasing, R., Mao, Y., & Ning, B. (2025). Monitoring the edges of product networks using distances. *Journal of Computer and System Sciences*, 148, 103602.
- Yang, C., Klasing, R., He, C., & Mao, Y. (2023). Perturbation results for distance-edge-monitoring numbers. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.02507*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.02507>.
- Yang, C., Klasing, R., Mao, Y., & Deng, X. (2024). On the distance-edge-monitoring numbers of graphs. *Discrete Applied Mathematics*, 342, 153–167.
- Yang, G., & He, C. (2023). Distance-edge-monitoring sets in hierarchical and corona graphs. *Journal of Interconnection Networks*, 23, 2250003.